

1 **Immunity at the maternal-fetal interface.**

2 Shahan K. Mamoor, B.S., M.S., Ph.D cand.¹
3 ¹shahanmamoor@gmail.com
4 Chestnut Hill, MA USA 02467
5 East Islip, NY USA 11730

6 We measured total transcription in two cell types at the maternal-fetal interface: fetal placental
7 macrophages and maternal intervillous monocytes. Maternal intervillous monocytes exhibited an altered
8 cellular identity profile marked by activation of *Twist1*, *Half* and *Hopx*, and silenced killer cell resources
9 including *Ncr3lg1*. The maternal intervillous monocytes activated *Muc15* and expressed *Cd200*. In contrast
10 to the fetal placental macrophages, the maternal intervillous monocytes did not express *Ezh2*, *Gzmk*, *Ii2rb*
11 or *Tnfrsf4*. Maternal intervillous monocytes expressed gliomedin (*Gldn*).
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13 Citations

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